

MU-MIMO and Multi-beam ISAC Hybrid Beamforming Design

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Abstract—This paper addresses the problem of fully-connected hybrid analog-digital (HAD) beamforming design for a multi-user and multi-beam ISAC systems. The traditional approaches to this problem involve a two-step process: first, a fully digital precoder is obtained, then the HAD beamforming is resolved by minimizing the Euclidean distance to the previously designed fully digital precoder. However, the main drawback of this method is that the communication or radio-sensing constraints considered in the first phase may be not preserved after the second one. In contrast, our work prioritizes preserving these constraints by directly designing the fully-connected HAD beamforming. We maximize the weighted sum rate while subject to power budget and radio-sensing constraints. To solve this, we propose an innovative iterative alternate optimization algorithm. Simulation results demonstrate a performance close to that of a fully digital precoder, outperforming previous fully-connected hybrid beamforming methods for ISAC.

Index Terms—MIMO; ISAC; wireless communication; radio-sensing; multi-beam steering, iterative alternate optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radar and wireless communication have traditionally evolved as separate radio systems, where national and international radio regulators have guaranteed interference-free operation [1]–[4]. However, the increasing demand for spectrum resources, driven by recent broadband radio systems has triggered research into more efficient coexistence paradigms between radar and wireless communication like projection-based and spectrum access methods [1], [2], [5], [6]. More recently, radar and communication communities have proposed the integration of communication and radar into a single platform, known as Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) [1], [4], [7].

ISAC promises to address the spectrum scarcity issue and efficiently utilize resources such as radio-frequency chains, antennas, and network infrastructure while pursuing mutual benefits for both sensing and communication functions. ISAC has been identified as a key technology for future wireless systems (i.e., 6G [8] and Wi-Fi [9]), enabling new services and use cases for various applications such as public safety, object and intruder, and fall detection for smart homes, weather monitoring, etc. Extensive academic research in recent years has focused on essential areas for ISAC, including waveform design, precoding and receiver design, fundamental information-theoretical limits, network architectures, and framework design. However, further research is still required about beamforming design methods. In the context of ISAC, beamforming refers to spatial signal processing, aiming to

efficiently support communication and radio-sensing applications simultaneously. The following provides a brief review of beamforming methods for ISAC [10]–[14].

In [10], the authors designed the precoding matrices that formulate an appropriate radio-sensing probing beampattern while guaranteeing that the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) of multiple communication users and total power budget constraints. The results demonstrated that the ISAC transmission yields better overall performance than the coexistence scenario, where antennas are separated to deliver communication and radio-sensing operations separately. Likewise, [11] designed the precoder that minimizes a radio-sensing loss function subject to power budget and SINR in a multi-user environment. This approach involved independent communication and radio-sensing precoders, resulting in improved radio-sensing performance compared to [10]. However, this enhancement came at the expense of increased interference to communication users.

The previous contributions focused on fully digital precoder design, which requires a radio-frequency (RF) chain for each antenna element. However, ISAC is expected to mainly operate on millimeter-wave (mmWave) bands and above, where fully-digital precoding would lead to increased complexity and power consumption. Consequently, as seen in the radar/communication fields, the ISAC community has also shown interest in the design of Hybrid Analog-Digital (HAD) architecture for ISAC [12]–[14]. However, different from radar or communication, the design of HAD beamforming for ISAC has to consider both communication and radar metrics, thereby increasing the complexity in the design of optimal precoding when compared to problems exclusively focused on communication or radar. In [12], the authors investigated the design of partially-connected hybrid beamforming for a single-user MIMO (SU-MIMO) ISAC scenario. They derived the optimal HAD beamforming matrices that minimize a weighted sum between communication and radar metrics, subject to the total power budget. This initial contribution was limited to partially-connected HAD architecture and SU-MIMO. The authors of [13] studied the design of fully-connected hybrid beamforming. It was also considered a SU-MIMO scenario. The method approximates a zero-forcing (ZF) precoder, where the analog precoder is set to point toward the direction of the radio-sensing steering vectors. That approach constrains the analog beamformer to an alphabet of steering vectors. More recently, [14] proposed the design of a fully-connected

hybrid beamforming for a multi-user MIMO (MU-MIMO) scenario. The method finds the precoder that minimizes the Euclidean distance of the transmit beam pattern to a previously devised radio-sensing transmit beam pattern, subject to SINR constraints of communication users and power budget. The authors considered a two-stage optimization approach. The main drawback of [14] is that it can not guarantee that the constraints considered in the first phase are preserved when resolving the HAD matrices in the second phase.

The drawbacks related to constraint preservation reported by two-stage optimization approaches motivated our work. We propose a communication-centric method to design the fully-connected hybrid beamforming, ensuring that the specified set of radio-sensing constraints is consistently fulfilled. This work considers the problem of fully-connected hybrid beamforming design for a multi-user and multi-target/beam ISAC scenario. A multi-antenna BS simultaneously transmits data toward single-antenna UEs while steering probing beams for object detection. The contribution of this work is the proposal of a novel algorithm for the design of hybrid beamforming for multi-user and multi-beam ISAC scenarios, always guaranteeing the fulfillment of the constraints.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the system model. Section III introduces the problem formulation, and details the alternate optimization algorithm. In Section IV, the proposed algorithm is assessed. Finally, Section V outlines the main conclusions of this paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The scenario depicted in Fig. 1 is examined in this work. Specifically, the dual-functional transmitter BS_{tx} simultaneously communicates with K single-antenna user equipment (UE) and steers Q radio-sensing probing beams (RSb) towards ϕ_q directions. The transmitter (BS_{tx}) is equipped with a uniform linear array (ULA) antenna holding N_{tx} elements.

Fig. 1. The considered multi-user/multi-beam ISAC scenario. An ISAC transmitter BS_{tx} jointly communicates with K single-antenna UEs and steers Q RSbs for target detection.

A. Transmitted Signal Model

We consider a downlink MU-MIMO transmission where the communication signal is also utilized for radio-sensing purposes [13]. The system operates in the mmWave band, and the BS_{tx} employs an HAD architecture with N_{RF} radio-frequency (RF) chains. In this scenario, the transmitted signal can be modeled by

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d \mathbf{s} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}} \times N_{\text{RF}}}$ represents the analog precoder, $\mathbf{W}_d = [\mathbf{w}_{d,1}, \dots, \mathbf{w}_{d,K}] \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{RF}} \times K}$ refers to the digital precoder, and $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^K$ denotes the transmitted data stream. It is assumed that the data stream transmitted to each user is independent and has unit power, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^H] = \mathbf{I}_K$. Additionally, we consider a fully-connected HAD architecture, where each RF chain is connected to all antenna elements via phase shifters, that is $|\mathbf{W}_a(i, j)| = \sqrt{N_{\text{tx}} N_{\text{RF}}^{-1}}$. The available power budget is constrained by P_T , such that

$$\|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T. \quad (2)$$

B. Communication Receiver Model

The signal received by the k th UE can be expressed as

$$y_k = \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,k} s_k + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \sum_{i=1, i \neq k}^K \mathbf{w}_{d,i} s_i + n_k \quad (3)$$

where the first term represents the desired signal, the second term models the inter-user interference, and n_k is additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) at the receiver, which has zero mean and variance σ_k^2 . The channel between the BS_{tx} and the k th UE is modelled by $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}}}$, and is characterized as a geometric channel [16].

From (3), the SINR of the k th UE can be expressed as

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,k}|^2}{\sum_{i \neq k} |\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,i}|^2 + \sigma_k^2}. \quad (4)$$

The rate of the k th UE is given by

$$R_k = \log(1 + \text{SINR}_k). \quad (5)$$

C. Radio-sensing Model

The considered radio-sensing metric is the power of the transmitted signal in the direction of the Q RSbs, which point towards $\phi_q \forall q$. The signal in the direction of the q th RSb is given by

$$g_q = \mathbf{g}_q^H \mathbf{W}_a \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{w}_{d,k} s_k, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{g}_q \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\text{tx}}}$ denotes the array response vector towards ϕ_q [12]. The power of the signal in the direction of ϕ_q can be represented by

$$G(\phi_q) = \sum_{k=1}^K |\mathbf{g}_q^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,k}|^2. \quad (7)$$

III. HYBRID BEAMFORMING DESIGN

This section introduces a novel algorithm for designing optimal fully-connected hybrid beamforming matrices. The original problem maximizes the weighted sum-rate [17], subject to power budget and radio-sensing constraints. However, the original formulation leads to a non-convex optimization problem, known to be challenging to solve [15], [17]. To address this, we exploit the equivalence between weighted sum-rate maximization and WMMSE minimization [15]. This reformulation allows us to leverage more tractable techniques for designing the optimal analog and digital beamforming matrices.

A. Problem Formulation

We aim to design the HAD beamforming matrices that maximize the weighted sum-rate of the downlink communication system. The solution is subject to constraints, the first constraint limits the total power budget and the second constraint ensures that the power in the direction of the RSBs is greater than a defined minimum bound value. The optimization problem can be formulated as follows

$$\max_{\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{W}_d} \sum_k \alpha_k R_k \quad (8a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T \quad (8b)$$

$$G(\phi_q) \geq \Delta_q, \forall q \quad (8c)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (8d)$$

where α_k weights the k th UE, Δ_q is the minimum bound value, and \mathcal{A} describes the feasible set of analog beamforming matrices (i.e., entries with CM).

B. WMMSE-Based Equivalent Optimization Problem

The considered optimization problem (8) is non-convex, which is due to the form of the objective function, constraints (8c) and (8d). However, we resort to the equivalence in [15], to formulate (8) into a more tractable form, given by

$$\min_{\mathbf{w}_a, \mathbf{w}_d, \omega_k, u_k} \sum_k \alpha_k \omega_k e_k - \log(\omega_k) \quad (9)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T$$

$$G(\phi_q) \geq \Delta_q, \forall q$$

$$\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathcal{A}$$

where ω_k and u_k represent a weight and equalizer at k th UE, respectively. Also, e_k refers to the mean squared error (MSE) between the transmitted signal s_k and the soft decision \hat{s}_k . The MSE is given by,

$$e_k = \mathbb{E}[(\hat{s}_k - s_k)(\hat{s}_k - s_k)^H]$$

$$= |1 - u_k^* \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,k}|^2 + \sum_{i \neq k} |u_k^* \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,i}|^2 \quad (10)$$

$$+ |u_k|^2 \sigma_{n_k}^2,$$

and $\hat{s}_k = u_k^* y_k$.

The previous states that minimizing the WMMSE is equivalent to maximizing the weighted sum-rate. However, due to the quadratic nature of the objective function of the WMMSE

problem, solving (9) is more tractable compared to (8). The solution to (9) can be obtained through alternate optimization, where both ω_k and u_k have closed-form solutions [15]. The optimal solution for u_k is given by

$$u_k^\circ = j_k^{-1} \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,k} \quad (11)$$

where $j_k = \sum_{i=1}^K |\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{w}_{d,i}|^2 + \sigma_k^2$ is the variance of the received signal. The optimal solution for ω_k is $\omega_k^\circ = e_k^{-1}$.

The CM and radio-sensing constraints make (9) a non-convex problem, where it is not possible to find a closed-form solution for \mathbf{W}_a and \mathbf{W}_d . Consequently, the following describes an iterative alternate algorithm for the hybrid beamforming design.

C. Iterative Algorithm for Hybrid Beamforming Design

This section introduces an iterative alternating algorithm to obtain \mathbf{W}_a and \mathbf{W}_d . As discussed earlier, solving (9) is challenging due to the non-convexity of (8c) and (8d). To address this, we replace constraint (8c) with a simpler convex constraint. Additionally, the non-convexity of (8d) is handled by resorting to transformations that provide a version of (9), where a solution for \mathbf{W}_a and \mathbf{W}_d can be found.

Fixing $\omega_k = \omega_k^\circ$ and $u_k = u_k^\circ$, and substituting (10) into (9), we can rewrite the problem as follows

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{W}_d} \|\Phi^{1/2} (\mathbf{I} - \Psi \mathbf{H}_{\text{UE}}^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d)\|_F^2 \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T \quad (12b)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{K}} \sum_k \Re(\mathbf{g}_q^H \mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d \mathbf{e}_k) = \Delta_q^{1/2} \quad \forall q \quad (12c)$$

$$\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathcal{A} \quad (12d)$$

where $\Phi = \text{diag}\{\alpha_1 \omega_1, \dots, \alpha_K \omega_K\}$, $\Psi = \text{diag}\{u_1^*, \dots, u_K^*\}$, and $\mathbf{H}_{\text{UE}} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_K]$.

The previous problem can be majorized as follows [18]

$$\min_{\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{W}_d} \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d - \hat{\mathbf{W}}_0\|_F^2 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T$$

$$\mathbf{W}_a \in \mathcal{A}$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{W}}_0 = \mathbf{W}_{a,0} \mathbf{W}_{d,0} - \alpha \nabla \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0}, \mathbf{W}_{d,0}, \mu_q^*), \quad (14)$$

$\mathbf{W}_{a,0}$, and $\mathbf{W}_{d,0}$ denote the previous iteration analog and digital precoders. Also, $\alpha = 1/\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{L}})$ denotes the inverse of the maximum eigenvalue of $\mathbf{H}_{\mathcal{L}} = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}}$. Additionally, the gradient $\nabla \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0}, \mathbf{W}_{d,0}, \mu_q)$ is given by

$$\nabla \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0} \mathbf{W}_{d,0}, \mu_q) = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}}^H \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}} \mathbf{W}_{a,0} \mathbf{W}_{d,0}$$

$$- \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}}^H \Phi^{1/2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_q \mu_q \mathbf{G}_q. \quad (15)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_{\text{UE}} = \Phi^{1/2} \Psi \mathbf{H}_{\text{UE}}^H$ represents an equivalent channel, and $\mathbf{G}_q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{K}} \mathbf{1}_{1 \times K} \otimes \mathbf{g}_q$ is the radio-sensing steering vector in matrix form.

The following subsections detail how the solutions for \mathbf{W}_a and \mathbf{W}_d are obtained.

1) *Analog Beamforming Design*: The analog precoder \mathbf{W}_a is given by,

$$\mathbf{W}_a = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{\text{tx}}N_{RF}}} \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0} - \beta \nabla f(\mathbf{W}_{a,0})), \quad (16)$$

where the gradient is given by,

$$\nabla f(\mathbf{W}_{a,0}) = (2\mathbf{W}_{a,0}\mathbf{W}_{d,0} - \hat{\mathbf{W}}_0)\mathbf{W}_{d,0}^H, \quad (17)$$

$\beta = 1/\lambda_{\max}(\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{w}_a))$ with $\mathbf{H}_f(\mathbf{w}_a) = 2\mathbf{W}_{d,0}\mathbf{W}_{d,0}^H$, and \mathcal{R} is a retraction over the complex circle manifold defined as,

$$\mathcal{R}(w) = \frac{w}{|w|} \quad (18)$$

where w is a complex scalar. For matrices, the retraction is applied to each entry.

2) *Digital Beamforming Design*: The optimal \mathbf{W}_d is given by,

$$\bar{\mathbf{W}}_d = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0}^H \mathbf{W}_{a,0})^{-1} \mathbf{W}_{a,0}^H \hat{\mathbf{W}}_0, \quad (19)$$

where the power constraint is satisfied through the projection

$$\mathbf{W}_d = \mathcal{P}(\mathbf{W}_{a,0}, 2\bar{\mathbf{W}}_d), \quad (20)$$

where

$$\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{W}_a, \mathbf{W}_d) = \begin{cases} \mathbf{W}_d, & \|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F^2 \leq P_T \\ \frac{\sqrt{P_T}}{\|\mathbf{W}_a \mathbf{W}_d\|_F} \mathbf{W}_d, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

All steps of the derivation ensure that the new objective majorizes the previous optimizations objective. Therefore, it is ensured that the proposed method strictly improves performance over the iterations.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section validates the proposed algorithm, referred to as ItAIHAD. Additionally, ItAIHAD is compared with the fully digital precoder and the algorithm in [14], referred to as TwoS-AltMin. Unless otherwise stated, the results are obtained for a ULA holding $N_{\text{tx}} = 32$, spaced $\lambda/2$. Additionally, the results are obtained for a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 20 dB. The communication channel \mathbf{h}_k (refer to [16]) consists of 10 paths, with phases uniformly distributed within $(-\pi/2, \pi/2]$, and complex gains following a Gaussian distribution with zero mean and unit variance. The power budget is set to $P_T = 1$, and the communication channels and steering vector are normalized, i.e., $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{h}_k] = \|\mathbf{g}_q\|^2 = 1$. Consequently, (7) can only take values between $(0, 1]$.

Fig. 2 shows the beampattern obtained for a scenario with three UEs with LoS ($K = 3$) and two RSBs ($Q = 2$). The UEs are positioned at $-45^\circ, 5^\circ, 35^\circ$, while the RSBs point towards $\phi_1 = -20^\circ$ and $\phi_2 = 15^\circ$. We consider that both RSBs have the same constraint, i.e., $\Delta_1 = \Delta_2$.

The results indicate a trade-off between the gain of the transmit beampattern towards the UEs and the RSBs. As the radio-sensing constraints Δ_1 and Δ_2 increase, the gain in the direction of the UEs reduces, which impacts negatively the sum-rate of UEs. The following investigates the trade-off between the sum-rate and the radio-sensing constraints.

Fig. 2. The transmitted beampattern obtained for $N_{\text{tx}} = 32$, $K = 3$, and $Q = 2$.

Fig. 3 illustrates the downlink sum-rate for values of the radio-sensing constraint (Δ) ranging from 0.1 to 0.9. The scenario under consideration involves two UEs ($K = 2$) and one RSB ($Q = 1$). Different configurations are assessed, i.e., $N_{RF} \in \{2, 4\}$. The ItAIHAD algorithm is compared with the fully digital precoder and the TwoS-AltMin algorithm. Please notice that to ensure fairness in the comparisons, the hybrid beamforming obtained via the TwoS-AltMin approximates a fully digital precoder resulting from the ItAIHAD algorithm by setting $N_{RF} = N_{\text{tx}}$.

Fig. 3. The mean sum-rate versus the radio-sensing constraint Δ obtained for ItAIHAD, fully-digital and TwoS-AltMin algorithms for a scenario with $K = 2$ and $Q = 1$.

The results from Fig. 3 indicate that for $N_{RF} = 2$, the ItAIHAD algorithm outperforms the TwoS-AltMin algorithm [14]. However, for $N_{RF} = 4$, both the ItAIHAD and TwoS-AltMin algorithms achieve the same performance as the fully digital precoder. The performance gap reported by the TwoS-AltMin for $N_{RF} = 2$ is due to the insufficient resources

available to perform the approximation to the previously obtained fully-digital precoder. Simulations have shown that the TwoS-AltMin algorithm achieves performance similar to the ItAIHAD and fully digital designs when the number of available RF chains is twice the number of UEs, i.e., $N_{RF} \geq 2K$. The ItAIHAD and fully digital designs report a zero percent outage probability, whereas the TwoS-AltMin algorithm does not. Consequently, Table I summarizes the outage probability obtained for the TwoS-AltMin algorithm for $N_{RF} = 2, 4$ and $\Delta = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5$.

TABLE I
THE OUTAGE PROBABILITY $P(G(\phi_1)) \leq \Delta_1$ OBTAINED FOR THE
TWO-S-ALTMIN ALGORITHM.

Δ_1	$N_{RF} = 2$	$N_{RF} = 4$
0.1	49%	8%
0.3	28%	11%
0.5	6%	8%

The results in Table I indicate that the TwoS-AltMin algorithm cannot consistently guarantee the fulfillment of the radio-sensing constraint (considered in the design of the fully digital precoder) (8c).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper addressed the problem of fully-connected hybrid beamforming design for MU-MIMO and multi-beam ISAC scenarios. The considered problem was the maximization of the weighted sum-rate subject to power budget and radio-sensing constraints, which presented a high complexity. Therefore, we leveraged the equivalence with the WMMSE problem, reformulating the original problem into a more tractable form. However, the hybrid architecture still precluded a closed-form solution. Hence, we proposed an iterative alternate optimization algorithm to design the fully-connected hybrid beamforming matrices. Simulations revealed that the proposed algorithm consistently fulfills the considered constraints, in contrast to the previous method in the literature. Also, it was demonstrated that the ItAIHAD outperforms the TwoS-AltMin algorithm and approaches the fully digital even when limited RF chains are available, leading to an energy-efficient solution.

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